

Proverbs or Idioms: A Cross-Cultural Analysis on How Proverbs or Idioms are Treated in Chinese and Bengali Language

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The principle finding of this study is to examine some common proverbs that are used in Chinese and Bengali including their counterparts to shed light on significant socio-cultural differences. The study is also going to put some light on the Chinese idioms that are used with certain common elements in Bengali proverbs and Chinese Proverbs as Bengali idioms. The choice of sample proverbs and idioms are collected from random sources; Chinese proverbs and idioms same as Bengali collected from Chinese classmates, friends, some online resources and books. It would be more a cross-cultural comparative study. Proverbs/প্রবাদ/谚语 are words which are encoded by the speaker and decoded by the listener by means of their underlined (background) knowledge of the language itself. Idiom/ বাগধারা /成语 on the other hand, is a group of words having a meaning, not deducible from those of the individual words. Idioms are pervasive in a language, reflecting its culture even more vividly and deeply than all other kinds of words. Proverbs and idioms, as metaphoric expressions or as cultural discourse, are codified on semantic structures. Thereby, proverbs and idioms are interpreted and negotiated with its pragmatic signification at linguistic, philosophical and cultural levels. Also proverbs and idioms reflect the cultural identity of a specific society and despite the uniqueness of languages and the profound differences between cultures and there are proverbs and idioms that shed light on universal truths of human life, common traditions and beliefs. Undoubtedly, these proverbs and idioms have bridged linguistic and cultural barriers throughout human history, that's what the present paper tries to find out.

Keywords: CHINESE/BENGALI PROVERBS– CHINESE/BENGALI IDIOMS– SIMILARITIES– DISSIMILARITIES

Introduction

Proverbs (প্রবাদ/谚语) are brief sayings that reveal a common truth and express the perceptions of a community based on experiences in life, society and the world. Folk proverbs and sayings are an integral part of the spiritual treasures of the culture and language of the people, the age-old wisdom and skills used by them - an important part of the culture of human language (Syzdykov, 2014, pp. 318-321). China's five thousand year civilization treasures a great number of proverbs and idioms, which can draw a clear bottom line to almost every situation. On the other hand, Bengali language also has a good history that includes many foreign language's words, phrases, idioms and proverbs translated form. The Bengali word that is used is 'probad', which translates to 'statement' or 'saying'. Bengali proverbs are sayings passed along orally through the generations. Bengali proverbs provide insight into the traditions, wisdom, spirit, folk belief, education and talents of the nation. Although transmitted over many generations, this study also found some differences in how the different countries viewed proverbs. Even the Bengali proverbs of Bangladesh are different from the proverbs used in West Bengal of India. This paper mainly concerns with the Bengali proverbs used in Bangladesh.

Idioms or বাগধারা or 成语 or English idioms, in a broad sense, they have a particular structure and meaning, including set phrases, proverbial sayings and a lot of slang expressions. In modern English, idioms refer to the habitual expression of a certain language, the special language of a certain country or nationality, the special dialect of a particular region, society or class, and the language style of famous works (Lyu & Li, 2020, pp. 708-712). In generally, Chinese idioms can be roughly divided into: proverbs(谚语), allusions(典故), chengyu(成语), xiehouyu(歇后语), slang(俚语), idiomatic expressions(惯用语), colloquial sayings(俗语), couplets(成对词) and so on. (Guo, 2016, p.129) Chengyu is one of the most familiar forms in Chinese idioms. (Lyu & Li, 2020, pp. 708-712)

The wisdom of Chinese traditional culture doesn't only reflect on the material civilization. The spiritual civilization is also splendid. Inventions and creations change life and make miracles, and through these practice, the working people of previous generations obtain a lot of experience about life. Then they summarized them as proverbs, which have been widely circulated among people from long ago. Sometimes they need these wise sayings to guide themselves in real life which is also common for Bengali and English proverb culture. Bengali proverbs are just as pertinent today. Below are examples of proverbs from Bangladesh.

1. “Half-truth is more dangerous than falsehood” (আধা সত্য মিথ্যা অপেক্ষা ভয়ংকর/ Ardha-Satya Mithya Apeksha Bhayankara)
2. “Thirteen festivals in twelve months” (বারো মাসে তের পর্বন /Baro Mashe Tero Parbon) – many occasions for celebrating.
3. “Time flows like the flow of water in a river” (সময় বহিয়া যায় নদীর স্রোতের প্রায়/ Shomoy Bohia Jaey Nodir Sroter Praye)
4. “This is a happy time of the Harvest for one, it is complete devastation for someone else” (কারো পৌষ মাস কারো সর্বনাশ/ Karo Poush Maash, Karo Shorbonash)
5. “Hide the fish with greens” (শাক দিয়ে মাছ ঢাকা/shak die machh dhaka)

6. “Saying something irrelevant to the present occasion” (ধান ভানতে শিবের গীত/ Dhan Bhante Shiber Geet)
7. “You cannot eat a fried fish by flipping it” (ভাজা মাছ উলটে খেতে পারে না/bhaja machh ultie khete pare na” – an inept person
8. “Since the Brahmin who owns the land is away, the hired ploughmen stop working” (বামুন গেলো ঘর তো লাঙ্গল তুলে ধার/ Bamun Gelo Ghar To Langal Tule Dhar)
9. “Think before you do, not after you’re done” (ভাবিয়া করিও কাজ করিয়া ভাবিও না/ Bhabia Korio Kaj, Korio Bhabio Na)
10. “A one-eyed uncle is better than no uncle at all” (নাই মামা থেকে কানা মামা ভালো/ Na mama theke kana mama bhalo)
11. “The eyes are the mirror of the mind” (চোখ মনের আয়না/ Chokh Moner Ayna) (Bangladeshi.com)

Bengali idioms like “আঙ্গুল ফুলে কলা গাছ/ Angul fule kola gas”, “চোখের বালি/Chokher bali”, “চাঁদের হাট/ Chader haat”, “আকাশ কুসুম কলনা/ Akash kusum kolona” and so on. Among all these proverbs and idioms some have some similarities with the Chinese proverbs and idioms and also some dissimilarity. Among these dissimilarities, there are some Chinese proverbs found used as Bengali idioms and Bengali idioms are found used as Chinese proverbs. So the present study is mostly the cross cultural study. The goal of the research is a cross-cultural analysis on how proverbs and idioms are treated in Chinese and Bengali language. The novelty and theoretical value of the research is that it is the first systematic study of the proverbs in two languages Chinese and Bengali. This comparative study on Proverbs and idioms improve cross-cultural awareness among students; thus foreign language teachers are expected to be inspired by the results of this research.

Literature Review

As an interesting and challenging area of language, idioms and proverbs have received special attention for analysis. Researchers usually choose specific language pairs for investigation, such as analysis of idioms or proverbs between English and Malay (Charteris-Black, 2003), English and Chinese (Liu, 2012), English and Arabic (Al-Shawi and Mahdi, 2012), English and Turkish (Ili, 2016), but a few to be mentioned. However, a cross-linguistic study of both idiom and proverbs is something rare. This is a gap in the literature that this paper aims to fill in, at least across the two chosen language pairs; Bengali and Chinese which also a rare analysis. Bagchi.T& Sarvaiya.A (2016) paper mainly studied and analysed the idioms in Bengali from a cognitive semantic viewpoint. Their paper deals with a collection of sixty random idioms from Bangla. The first section is a general introduction to the concepts of idioms and Cognitive Semantics. The second section covers the analysis of the structure of idioms and their classification based on their semantic structure. The third section analysed the application of Cognitive Semantic concepts of the idioms. The fourth and final section has conclusions based on these analyses in Bangla.

Syarfuni (2014, pp 26-50) study described a study about an analysis of English and Indonesian idioms and

proverbs. This research purposed to analyze the differences and similarities between English and Indonesian idioms and proverbs that used in daily life. Idiom is a set of word that had different meaning from the basic word. The methodology of this study is library research. Based on researcher analysis English and Indonesian idioms and proverbs, actually almost the same in meaning, but they have their own culture to be delivered the ideas about idioms and proverbs. It is misunderstanding among the people when they have to deliver the proverb in different culture and societies. So the writer concluded that there are similarities and differences between idioms and proverbs of English and Indonesian but it is depended on their culture. Although the present paper of our mainly concentrates on how the proverb and idioms are treated in two languages.

In one paper of Neale (2015) that investigated the meaning of similar English and Japanese proverbs semantically. It uses textual data sourced from online corpora to highlight and compare the different cultural and conceptual elements embedded within these proverbs. The findings of this investigation demonstrate that matching proverbs from different languages is a potentially problematic exercise, both in dictionaries and in the second-language classroom. Japanese proverb dictionaries, such as the *Shinmeikai koji kotowaza jiten* (2007), the *Kotowaza no izumi* (Takashima 1981) and the *Nichiei hikaku kotowaza jiten* (Yamamoto 2007), offer English equivalents to the Japanese proverbs (called *kotowaza*) that they list.¹ However, there are subtle differences between some of the proverbs that these dictionaries pair together. For example, the Japanese proverb, 'Nen ni wa nen o ireyo (念には念を入れよ)', for example. The *Shinmeikai* dictionary offers 'Look before you leap' as an English equivalent (2007, 492).

Nikolaeva, Shumei & Panina (2017) studied of ethnic proverbs in intercultural communication in English has recently become a promising research perspective. The abundance uses of Chinese native Proverb is noticed in Chinese media in English, which communicate China's message to the world. In media coverage of international issues these proverbs present an extremely effective tool of China's interaction with other countries. Proverbs convey China's standpoint indirectly but firmly and may be viewed as China's discursive strategy in media-based international discourse. The research of Nikolaeva, Shumei & Panina (2017), deals with the questions of intercultural and international pragmatics of Chinese proverb quotations in Chinese media in English. The analysis was done on China's intentions with native proverb quotations and other countries' reactions to the proverb utterances.

Just as the same, (Schafroth, 2020, pp 129-150), in his recent paper, examined the question of whether (or to what extent) equivalence between idiomatic expressions in different languages is possible. As equivalence is understood in a broad sense to include all linguistic levels and all types of knowledge about a phraseological unit, it turns out to be very difficult to maintain the claim of interlingual equivalence with regard to idioms. Based on the theoretical framework of Construction Grammar and focusing on linguistic data provided by corpora, he discussed some types of pseudo-equivalence between Italian and German idioms, also taking into account other languages. The objective of this article is to raise awareness among foreign languages teachers and learners as well as among linguists about the main types of idiosyncrasy that characterize phraseological

units.

In another recent paper by Leksono& Jantem (2020, pp 1-10) works on a paper containing Thai and Indonesian idioms that refer to the body parts. They mentioned the Thai and Indonesian language are often studied as a Second language by the Thai and Indonesian people. The findings revealed three categories of idiomatic expressions, first, a list of the 15 idioms that have same literal and figurative meaning. Second, 20 idioms differ in real meaning but are similar in literal meanings and 10 idioms that differ in literal meaning but are similar in real meaning. In each category there are similar and different meanings. Just as the same way our paper also make such division following the paper but the present paper more concentrates on how differently proverbs and idioms are treated in the two culture and language.

Rasul.S.H (2018, pp 121-141) explored the translation of idioms across a set of languages (English, Arabic, French, Kurdish, Persian and Turkish), applying Baker's (1992/2011) strategies for translating idioms. The paper first examined Baker's strategies as to whether they can be considered a practical model to extrapolate in rendering idioms across languages. Secondly, given the type of strategies employed, the study attempts to find out whether idioms can be treated as a culture-specific or universal phenomenon. So unlike the present paper Rasul.S.H (2018, pp 121-141) mainly focus on translation.

All the above studies contain the overall ideas how the present paper is going to end up its conclusion but the difference lies in the outcome of the research. The present research paper mainly finds out the difference comparing it with the similarity in case of using the proverbs mainly and also touching on certain idioms in Bengali and Chinese Culture which have not been studied in past.

Methodology

Researcher approaches a qualitative descriptive to do the research. The paper mainly follow the qualitative methodology collecting data from different source that would lead to its conclusion. This study mainly try to include the data as quasi- corpora somewhat. To justify the first question researcher adapted the qualitative descriptive study to find out whether there are any similarities in Chinese and Bengali language in term of using of proverbs or not. For the second questions which is more an important part of the paper, as the question would find the answer of how different that these two cultures have including how different they are treated in Chinese and English language.

The research questions are following:

1. What are the similarities in case of using proverbs in Chinese and Bengali language have?
2. How differently the idioms and and proverbs are treated in Chinese and Bengali language?

Data Analysis

Similarities in Case of Using Proverbs:

Both the Chinese and Bengali cultures and ideas have a lots commonality as both belong to Asian continent. So these languages also have some similarities the way the proverbs are spoken and used in both the cultural. Though there are lots of dissimilarities too. But all the proverbs are semantically universal in one or another way. The following are the examples of the similar and close meaningful proverbs that are used both in Chinese and Bengali languages:

Table 1: Similar/ Close meaningful Chinese and Bengali Proverbs

Chinese Proverbs	Bengali Proverbs	Similar/ Close meaning
1. 患难见朋友 A friend in need is a friend indeed.	দুঃসময়ের বন্ধুই প্রকৃত বন্ধু। (Dussomoyer bondhui prokirito bondhu.) A friend in need is a friend indeed.	Similar
2. 众志成城 (Unity is Strength)	একতাই বল।(Ekotai bol.) (Unity is Strength.)	Similar
3. 几家欢喜几家愁 (While some are happy, some are anxious.)	কারো পৌষ মাস কারো সর্বনাশ।(Karo poush magh, karo shorbonash.) One man's disaster is another man's delight.	Close meaning
4. 一举两得 (one move two gains.)	এক ঢিলে দুই পাখি মারা। (Ek dhile dui pakhi mara.) To kill two birds with one stone. Two benefits from one action.	Similar
5. 大智若愚 Great wisdom can seem foolish and great intelligence may appear to be stupidity.	অতি চালাকে গলায় দরি।(Oti chalak er golae dori.) Too crafty a person ends up on the gallows.	Close meaning
6. 三个和尚没有水可喝。 Three monks have no water to drink.	অতি সন্ন্যাসীতে গাজন নষ্ট।(Oti shonnashite gajon noshto.) Too many monks presiding can ruin the holy festivity.	Close meaning
7. 让你不能喝的水流過 Let the water you cannot drink, flow by.	আঙ্গুল ফল টক।(Angur fol tok.) Grapes are sour.	Close meaning
8. 一個人的運氣和命運會隨著時間而改變	আজ আমির তো কাল ফকির। (Aj amir, kaal fokir)	Close meaning

One's luck and one's destiny will change with time	Today I am rich (Muslim nobleman) tomorrow I am a pauper/poor man. Life is not uniform, time changes for better or worse.	
9. 美味的早餐不能代替豐盛的晚餐 A good breakfast is no substitute for a large dinner.	আম না পেয়ে আঁটি চোষা। (Aam na peye ati chosha.) When you don't get the mango, suck its stone (if you can). You really cannot substitute a derivative for something genuine.	Close meaning
10. 一隻手不能鼓掌 One hand cannot applaud.	এক হাতে তালি বাজে নাহ। (Ek haate tali baje na.) You cannot clap with one hand. One cannot do what it takes two to do.	Similar
11. 如果你有錢，你可以讓魔鬼推你的磨刀石 If you have money, you can make the devil push your grindstone.	কড়ি তে বাঘের দুধ মিলে। (Kori te bagher dudh mile.) If you have the cowries (money), you can even buy tiger's milk. Money can buy anything. Money makes the mare go.	Close meaning
12. 搬山的人首先帶走小石頭 The man who removes a mountain begins by carrying away small stones.	কাঠবিড়ালির সাগর বাধা। (Kathbiralir shagor badha.) The squirrels building a bridge across the ocean. Sum total of small efforts can be significant.	Close meaning
13. 黑狗得到食物，白狗得到責備 The black dog gets the food; the white dog gets the blame.	দই খেল রামাকান্ত, বিচারের বেলায় গোর বর্ধন। (Doi khelen romakanto, bicharer belae gobordhon.) It was Ramakanta who stole the curd, but you are trying Gobardhan for the crime. To ascribe someone's fault to someone else.	Close meaning
14. 三個人可以組成一隻老虎 Three people can form a tiger.	দশ চক্রে ভাগ্যবান ভূত। (Dosh chokre bhogoban bhoot.) God becomes a ghost because ten people assert so. Even a very intelligent man may be	Close meaning

Three people can make up a tiger.	cornered or pushed to the wall by the intrigue or bad counsel of the many.	
15. 指著一隻鹿，稱其為馬 Point at a deer and call it a horse	দিন কে রাত করা। Din ke raat kora. To turn day into night. To exaggerate beyond recognition. To tell a down right lie.	Close meaning
16. 切勿用一隻手抓兩隻青蛙 Never try to catch two frogs with one hand.	দুই নৌকায় পা দেয়া। (Dui noukae paa deoya.) To stand on two boats with one leg in each. Not to be able to decide between two options.	Close meaning
17. 一份美味的早餐不能代替豐盛的晚餐。 A good breakfast is no substitute for a large dinner.	দুধের সাধ ঘোলে মেটে নাহ। (Dudher shadh ghole mete na.) You cannot satisfy the craving for milk with a yogurt drink. To console oneself with a base substitute.	Close meaning
18. 牆壁的另一側總是有耳朵 There are always ears on the other side of the wall.	দেয়ালের ও কান আছে। (Deyalero kaan ache.) Even walls have ears. You can never be sure who is eavesdropping.	Similar
19. 傲慢的軍隊肯定會輸掉這場戰鬥 An arrogant army will lose the battle for sure.	অতি দর্পে হোতা লঙ্কা। (Oti dorpe hota lanka.) Excessive bravado ruined the great kingdom of Lanka. Pride goes before fall.	Close meaning
20. 在風吹拂之前，蘆葦叢生，而強大的橡樹卻倒下了。 A reed before the wind lives on, while the mighty oaks do fall.	অতি বাড় বেড়ও নাক ঝড়ে পড়ে যাবে, অতি ছোট হোয়ও নাক ছাগলে মোড়াবে। (Oti baar bero nako jhore pore jabe, oti choto hoyo nako chagole morabe.) Don't grow too tall (like a tree) for the storm can fell you, don't remain too	Close meaning

	<p>short (as a shrub) for the goat can devour you.</p> <p>Too much boasting or modesty - neither is good. Pride will have a fall.</p>	
<p>20. 雖然您住在森林附近，但不 要浪費柴火</p> <p>Though you live near a forest, do not waste firewood.</p>	<p>অনেক যদি মাছ পায় বিড়াল কাটা বেঁছে থায়। (Onek jodi mach pay, beral kata beche khac.)</p> <p>With an abundant supply of fish, even the cat discards the bones.</p> <p>When there is abundance, you are apt to pick and choose.</p>	Close meaning
<p>21. 胸襟寬廣地看到不 同宗教的真理，胸 襟寬闊地看到不同 的宗教。</p> <p>The broad-minded see the truth in different religions, the narrow-minded see only the differences</p>	<p>একং শদিপ্রা বুদ্ধা বধুপতি। (Ekong shodipra bohudha bodopti.)</p> <p>Truth is one, but saints call it by many names.</p> <p>There is only one God, but many religions.</p>	Close meaning
<p>22. 路遥知马力，日久 见人心。(lù yáo zhī mǎ lì, rì jiǔ jiàn rén xīn.)</p> <p><i>Just as distance tests a horse's strength, time can reveal a person's heart.</i> This proverb tells us that time tries all. So do not give a subjective assertion on anything blindly. Just let your cognition grow as time goes on.</p>	<p>সময়ই কথা বলবে। (somoj e kotha bolbe)</p> <p>(Time will say)</p>	Closed meaning
<p>23. 一口吃不成胖子。 (yīkǒu chī bù chéng pàngzi.)</p> <p><i>One meal won't make a fat man.</i> It means that you can't build up the constitution on one mouthful. Nobody could get instant benefits,</p>	<p>গাইতে গাইতে গায়েন, বাজাতে বাজাতে বায়েন(gaitte gaitte gayen, bajte bajte bayen)</p> <p>Perseverance makes one efficient</p>	Close meaning

<p>and success comes from the regular accumulation.</p>		
<p>24. 冰冻三尺，非一日之寒。(bīng dòng sānchǐ, fēi yí rì zhī hán.)</p> <p><i>It takes more than one cold day for the river to freeze three feet deep.</i></p> <p>There is a proverb in English which is universally known: “Rome was not built in a day.” The meaning of these two proverbs is exactly the same. So keep on working hard and be stick to it. Long-term efforts can contribute to achievement.</p>	<p>সিন্ধু সভ্যতা এক দিনে গড়ে উঠে নি। (Sindhu sovvota ek dine gore uthe ni)</p> <p>“Rome was not built in a day.”</p>	<p>similar</p>
<p>25. 由俭入奢易，由奢入俭难。(yóu jiǎn rùshē yì, yóu shē rùjiǎn nán.)</p> <p><i>It is easy to adapt it if ones living condition ascends from economical to luxurious; conversely, that becomes hard.</i></p> <p>Life contains many ups and downs, no one can go smoothly. So we should keep a gentle attitude to life. No matter in what kind of living condition, developing a good habit of thrift is necessary.</p>	<p>জীবন কন্টকময়। (jibon kontokamoy)</p> <p>Life is a bed of thorn</p>	<p>similar</p>
<p>26. 只要功夫深，铁杵磨成针。(zhǐyào gōngfu shēn, tiě chǔ mó chéng zhēn.)</p> <p><i>If you work hard enough at it, you can grind even an iron rod down to a needle.</i></p>	<p>পরিশ্রম ভাগ্যের প্রসূতি। (porishshrom vagger prosuti)</p> <p>Perseverance is the key to success.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>

<p>It means that constant dropping will wear away a stone. So be patient with any issue, and persistent efforts can solve any problem.</p>		
<p>27. 人不可貌相。(rén bù kě mào xiàng.)</p> <p><i>Never judge a person by his appearance.</i> It presents the same meaning as “never judge a book by its cover”.</p>	<p>চকচক করলেই সোনা হয় না। (Chok chok korlei shona hoyna.)</p> <p>Even if it shines, it does not mean its gold.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>28. 姜还是老的辣。(jiāng hái shì lǎo de là.) <i>Aged ginger is more pungent.</i> It means that the older, the wiser. So you’d better not close your ears to the elders, or you may be suffering losses.</p>	<p>বাতাসে চুল পাকে নাই। (batase chul pake nay)</p> <p>Indicating experience</p>	<p>similarity</p>
<p>29. 耳听为虚，眼见为实。(ěr tīng wéi xū, yǎn jiàn wéi shí.)</p> <p><i>What you hear about may be false; what you see is true.</i> This proverb tells us that we’d better not believe rumors easily. It’s more reliable if we could verify it by ourselves.</p>	<p>শোনা কথায় কান দিতে নেই। (Shona kothay kan dite ney)</p> <p>Don’t listen to what you hear.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>30. 小洞不补，大洞吃苦。(Xiǎodòng bù bǔ, dàdòng chī kǔ.'small hole not mend; big hole eat hardship') — If small holes aren't</p>	<p>সময়ের এক ফোঁড়় অসময়ের দশ ফোঁড়়। (Somoyer ek for osomoyer dosh for)</p> <p>A stitch in time saves nine</p>	<p>Similar</p>

<p>fixed, then big holes will bring hardship.</p> <p>This proverb tells us that if a trivial problem is not solved in time, it will become a serious and knotty one. Similar to: "A stitch in time saves nine."</p>		
<p>31. 水满则溢。 (Shuǐmǎn zé yì. 'water full but overflows') — Water flows in only to flow out.</p> <p>Similar to "what comes up must come down", this proverb points out that: things reverse when they reach their extremes. It's from the 18th century novel "A Dream of Red Mansions".</p>	<p>যেমন কর্ম তেমন ফল। (Jemon kormo temon fol)</p> <p>You reap what you sow.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>32. 留得青山在，不怕没柴烧。 (Liú dé qīngshān zài, búpà méi chái shāo. 'remain green hills present, not fear no firewood burn') — While there are green hills, there'll be wood to burn.</p> <p>i.e. "Where there is life, there is hope."</p>	<p>যতক্ষণ শ্বাস ততক্ষণ আঁশ। (Jotokkhon shash totokkhon aasshh)</p> <p>Where there is life, there is hope</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>33. 一鸟在手胜过双鸟在林。 (Yī niǎo zài shǒu shèng guò shuāng niǎo zài lín 'one bird in hand beats pair birds in forest') — A bird in the hand is worth than two in the bush.</p>	<p>গাছের দশটা থেকে পাতের একটাই ভাল (gacer doshta pata theke pater ektay valo) A bird in the hand is worth than two in the bush.</p>	<p>Similar</p>

<p>34. 难得糊涂。(Nándé hǔtu. 'hard get confusion') — Ignorance is bliss.</p> <p>Or: "Where ignorance is bliss, it's folly to be wise."</p>	<p>হাতি ঘোড়া গেল তল, মশা বলে কত জল (haati ghora gelo tol, mosha bole koto jol)</p> <p>Where wise people fails, Foolish pokes their nose</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>35. 祸从口出。(Huò cóng kǒu chū. 'disaster from mouth exits') — Disaster comes from careless talk.</p>	<p>মুখ দিয়ে যে কথা একবার বেরিয়ে যায় তা আর ফিরিয়ে আনা সম্ভব নাহ। (much diye je kotha ekbar beriye jai ta ar firiye ana sombov nah)</p> <p>A word once spoken is past recalling.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>36. 三人一条心，黄土变成金。(Sānrén yìtiáoxīn, huángtǔ biàn chéng jīn. 'three people one heart; yellow earth become gold') — If people are of one heart, even loess can become gold.</p> <p>This proverb tells us that as long as people are unified, any goal can be achieved.</p>	<p>একতায় বল। (Etotay bol)</p> <p>Unity is the strength</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>37. 身正不怕影子斜。(Shēnzhèng búpà yǐngzi xié. 'body straight not fear shadow slanting') — One who stands straight doesn't fear a crooked shadow.</p> <p>Similar to: "A straight foot is not afraid of a crooked shoe." i.e. A righteous man is not afraid to seem unrighteous.</p>	<p>চেনা বামনের পিতা লাগে নাহ। (Chena bamoner pita lage nah)</p> <p>A worthy man does not need any recommendation.</p>	<p>Close meaning.</p>
<p>38. 蜡烛照亮别人，却毁灭了自己。(Làzhú zhàoliàng biérén, què huǐmíè)</p>	<p>কেউ মরে বিল ছেঁচে, কেউ খাই কে। (kew more bill cheche, kew khay koy)</p> <p>One's sacrifice others take benefits</p>	<p>Similar</p>

<p>le zǐjǐ. 'candle illuminates others, yet destroys itself') — A candle lights others and consumes itself.</p> <p>This refers to self-sacrifice for the benefit of others.</p>		
<p>39. 种瓜得瓜，种豆得豆。(Zhòngguā dé guā, zhòngdòu dé dòu. 'sow melons reap melons; sow beans reap beans') — You reap what you sow.</p> <p>This proverb warns that one receives just returns for one's actions; good for good, and evil for evil. It's similar to the Biblical: "...whatsoever a man soweth, that shall he also reap."</p>	<p>যেমন কর্ম তেমন ফল। (Jemon kormo temon Fol.)</p> <p>What you will do in life, will get in return as a result.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>40. 患难见真情。(Huànnàn jiàn zhēnqíng 'Hardship see true situation') — In hardship we see true friendship.</p> <p>Similar to: "A friend in need is a friend indeed."</p>	<p>অসময়ের বন্ধুই প্রকৃত বন্ধু। (Oshomoyer bondhui prokrito bondhu.)</p> <p>A friend in need is a friend indeed.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>41. 入乡随俗。(Rù xiāng suí sú 'enter district follow custom') — When entering a locality follow the local customs.</p> <p>Like: "When in Rome, do as the Romans do."</p>	<p>যেখানে যেমন সেখানে তেমন (Jekhane jemon shekhane temon.)</p> <p>When in Rome, do as the Romans do.</p>	<p>Similar</p>

<p>42. 凡人不可貌相，海水不可斗量。 (Fánrén bù kě màoxiàng, hǎishuǐ bù kě dòuliàng. 'mortals can't judge by appearance, sea water can't cup measure') — Man cannot be judged by looks; seas cannot be measured by cup.</p> <p>In short: "don't judge by appearances".</p>	<p>চকচক করলেই সোনা হয় নাহ। (Chok chok korlei shona hoyna.)</p> <p>Even it shines; it doesn't mean its gold.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>43. 欲速则不达。(Yù sù zé bùdá. 'Desire speed but not attain.') — Those who just want speed don't succeed.</p>	<p>জলদির কাজ শয়তানের কাজ। (Joldir kaj soytaner kaj)</p> <p>Hasten work is devil's work</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>44. 有其父，必有其子。(Yǒuqífù, bìyǒuqízǐ. 'have his father, must have his son') — Where there's a father, there's his son.</p> <p>I.e. "Like father, like son."</p>	<p>বাপ কা বেটা সিপাইকা ঘোরা। (Baap ka beta, shipaika ghora.)</p> <p>Like father, like son.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>45. 机不可失，时不再来。(Jī bùkě shī, shí búzài lái. 'Opportunity can't lose, time not again come') — Don't miss opportunities: time doesn't come round again.</p> <p>Opportunity knocks but once.</p>	<p>ঝোপ বুঝে কোপ মারা। (Jhop buje kop mara)</p> <p>Utilize the opportunity</p>	<p>Close Meaning</p>

<p>46. 失败是成功之母。 (Shībài shì chénggōng zhī mǔ. 'failure is success's mother') — Failure is the mother of success.</p>	<p>ব্যর্থতা সাফল্যের মূল চাবিকাঠি। (Berthota shafoller mul chabikathi.)</p> <p>Failure is the key to success.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>47. 否极泰来。 (Pǐ jí tài lái. 'evil extreme peace come') — Peace replaces extreme evil.</p> <p>I.e. all nightmares end.</p>	<p>ঝড় থেমে গেলে সব শান্ত হয়ে যায়। (Jhor theme gele sob shanto hoye jay)</p> <p>After a storm everything goes quiet.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>48. 吃得苦中苦，方为人上人。 (Chī dé kǔzhōngkǔ, fāng wéi rénshàng rén. 'eat gain pain in pain, method for man on man') — Enduring deepening pain is how man ascends.</p> <p>I.e. "No pain, no gain."</p>	<p>কষ্ট না করলে কেউ মিলে নাহ।</p> <p>(kosto na korle kesto mile nah)</p> <p>"No pain, no gain."</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>49. 守得云开见月明。 (Shǒu dé yún kāi jiàn yuè míng. 'keep-watch gain cloud open see moonlight') — Watch till clouds part to see moonlight.</p> <p>I.e. "Every cloud has a silver lining" or trouble will pass.</p>	<p>দুঃখের পরে সুখ আসে। (Dukher por sukh ase) After trouble good time comes.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>50. 不能一口吃成胖子。 (Bùnéng yīkǒu chī chéng pàngzi. 'can't one mouthful eat become fat-person') — you can't</p>	<p>একবার না পারিলে দেখ শত বার। (Ekbar na parile dekho shotobar.)</p> <p>If you don't succeed the first time, try a hundred times.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>

<p>get fat with one mouthful.</p> <p>I.e. Some things aren't accomplished in a moment. Don't give up!</p>		
<p>51. 好书如挚友。 (Hǎoshū rú zhìyǒu. 'good book as-good-as close-friend') — A good book is like a good friend.</p>	<p>বই মানুষের সেরা বন্ধু। (boi manusher sera bondhu) Book is man's best friend.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>52. 一寸光阴一寸金， 寸金难买寸光阴。 (Yícùn guāngyīn yícùnjīn, cùnjīn nán mǎi cùnguāngyīn. '1 cun [Chinese inch, 1/30 m] time 1 cun gold, cun gold difficult buy cun time') — An inch of time is worth an inch of gold, but an inch of gold may not buy an inch of time.</p> <p>I.e. time is money, but it's difficult to buy time.</p>	<p>সময়ের মূল অনেক বেশি। (somoier mullo onek beshi) Time is money</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>53. 事实胜于雄辩。 (Shìshí shèng yú xióngbiàn.) — Facts beat eloquence.</p> <p>From Lu Xun's "Hot Wind" (鲁迅《热风题记》), it's like, "Actions speak louder than words."</p>	<p>কথায় কথা বাড়ে, ভোজনে পেট বাড়ে। (Kothae kotha bare, bhojone pet bare.) Actions speak louder than words.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>54. 三思而后行。 (Sānsī ér hòu xíng. "three thoughts and after act") — Think thrice before you act.</p>	<p>ভাবিয়া করিয় কাজ, করিয়া ভাবিয় না। (Bhabia korio kaaj, koria bhabio na.) Look before you leap, Think before you act</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>

<p>From "The Analects" (《论语》), it's like: "Look before you leap."</p>		
<p>55. 几家欢喜几家愁。 (Jǐjiā huānxǐ jǐjiā chōu. 'few families happy few families worried') — While some are happy, some are anxious.</p> <p>It means: one man's disaster is another man's delight.</p>	<p>কারো পৌষ মাস কারো সর্বনাশ। (Karo poushmagh karo shobonash.)</p> <p>One man's disaster is another man's delight.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>
<p>56. 一举两得。(Yī jǔ liǎng dé. 'one move two gains') — Two benefits from one action.</p> <p>Variously attributed to "History of the Later Han Dynasty" (c. 200), "The Book of Jin" (420), "Stories to Caution the World" (1624, Feng Menglong), and Lu Xun's collected letters, this is the Chinese version of "to kill two birds with one stone" (一石二鸟。Yīshíèrniǎo. 'one stone two birds'), possibly of Ovid.</p>	<p>এক ডিলে দুই পাখি মারা। (Ek dile dui pakhi mara.)</p> <p>Two benefits from one action.</p>	<p>Similar</p>
<p>57. 大智若愚。(Dàzhì ruò yú. 'great wisdom seem stupid') — Great wisdom can seem foolish.</p> <p>From "Laozi" (《老子》), it means: great intelligence may appear to be stupidity, and is sometimes used to describe a situation where "he knows most who speaks least".</p>	<p>অতি চালাকে গলায় দড়ি। (Oti chalak er golae dori.)</p> <p>Too crafty a person ends up on the gallows.</p>	<p>Close meaning</p>

<p>58. 一个萝卜一个坑 儿。 (Yīgè luóbo yīgè kēngr. 'one turnip one hole') — Each has his own task, and nobody is dispensable.</p> <p>i.e. "each to his own", "horses for courses", or "every kettle has its lid".</p>	<p>নিজের চরকায় তেল দেয়া (nijer chorkay tel deya) to mind one's own business.</p>	<p>Closed meaning</p>
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All of these data are collected from different online sources mentioned in reference section including researcher's own observations. So this numerous of proverb in Chinese and Bengali culture and language with the same utilization indicates the both language shares a lot in commonality. But at the same time they have some differences too.

Differences in Case of Using Proverbs and Idioms in Chinese and Bengali Languages

While analyzing the data the first difference that has been observed that in case of the use of proverb, in Chinese, all proverbs contains a morale lesson than just saying that has been used for a long time. On the other hand in case of Bengali Proverbs, they are mostly the peoples saying out of years experiences that becomes universal and pragmatically used generation after generation.

Then again as Bangladesh has been one of the colonized portions of Indian continent ruled by England, English language influence on Bengali proverb rather than idioms is not an unnoticeable area. But Bengali culture, history and religion have its influence on most of the proverbs and idioms that makes the difference in English and Bengali Proverbs and idioms. On the other hand, Chinese language doesn't have complete such extreme commonality with English as most of the proverbs and idioms are more influenced by the Chinese enormous philosophy, culture rather than religion and history.

But some Chinese proverbs have also tendencies to use like Bengali idioms semantically and Bengali idioms are also found to use like Chinese proverbs when it comes to meaning.

So based on all of these analyses the following table contains all the differences mentioned above:

Table 2: Differences in Case of Using Proverbs and Idioms

Chinese Proverbs	Bengali Proverbs/Idioms	Differences
<p>1. 不善始者不善终。 (Bú shànshǐzhě bù shànzhōng. 'not good starter not good</p>	<p>শেষ ভাল যার সব ভাল তার। (sheesh valo jar sob valo tar)</p>	<p>Dissimilarity It seems that in Chinese Beginning is important to have a good ending</p>

<p>end') — A bad beginning makes a bad ending.</p>	<p>Whose end is good everything is good.</p>	<p>but in Bengali ending is given more importance than beginning.</p>
<p>2. 家家有本难念的经。 (Jiājiā yǒu běn nán niàn de jīng. 'Every-family has own difficult remembered experience.') — Every family has its problems.</p> <p>Or: "There're skeletons in every family's closet."</p>	<p>নগর পুড়িলে দেবালয় কি এড়ায়। (Nagor purile debaloy ki eray) If one member in danger then the whole family have to suffer</p>	<p>This Chinese proverb is meaningfully used in Bengali as idioms than proverbs.</p>
<p>3. 先到先得。(Xiān dào xiān dé. 'first arrive first get') — The first to arrive is the first to succeed.</p> <p>i.e. "the early bird catches the worm."</p>	<p>আগে আসলে বাঘে খাই পিছে গেলে স্বর্ণ পায়।</p>	<p>Dissimilarity It seems that in Chinese Beginning is important to have a good ending but in Bengali ending is given more importance than beginning.</p>
<p>4. 即使是最足智多謀的家庭主婦也無法從無米飯的儲藏室中創造奇蹟</p> <p>Even the most resourceful housewife cannot create miracles from a riceless pantry.</p>	<p>অঘটন ঘটন পটীয়াসী। (Oghoton ghoton potiyoshi)</p> <p>A female skilled in bringing about what is impossible.</p> <p>One who can make the difficult or the impossible happen.</p>	<p>This Chinese proverb is meaningfully used in Bengali as idioms than proverbs.</p>

<p>5. 脚踏实地 (jiǎotàshídì) 脚踏实地 literally means “to step on solid ground.” It means that, like Warren Buffet, you work hard, focus on the fundamentals, and proceed in a steady and stable fashion. It’s an extremely positive chengyu. Here’s an example : “现在我们要继续脚踏实地” “xiànzàiwǒmenyàojìxùjiǎotàshídì” “Right now we need to continue staying grounded and pushing ahead”</p>	<p>গাইতে গাইতে গায়েন, বাজাতে বাজাতে বায়েন(gaitē gaitē gayēn, bajtē bajtē bayēn)</p> <p>Perseverance makes one efficient</p>	<p>This Chinese idiom is meaningfully used in Bengali as proverb.</p>
<p>6. 九牛一毛 (jiǔniúyīmáo) 九牛一毛 literally means “9 cows and 1 strand of cow hair.” It indicates something that’s so small that it’s like one strand of cow hair among 9 cows. Here’s an example: “电子商务的盈利在中国整体商业环境中简直是九牛一毛。” “diànzǐshāngwù de yínglìzài zhōngguó zhěngtǐ shāngyè huánjìng zhōng jiǎnz hǐshì jiǔniúyīmáo.” “In the entire Chinese commercial environment, the profits from E-commerce are simply just a drop in the bucket.”</p>	<p>বিন্দু থেকে সিন্দু হয়। (Bindu theke sindhu hoy)</p> <p>A small portion becomes a bigger part.</p>	<p>This Chinese idiom has been used with opposite meaning in Bengali language but as a proverb.</p>
<p>7. 损人利己 (sǔn rén lì jǐ): “to seek benefit at the expense of others”</p>	<p>কেউ মরে বিল ছেঁচে, কেউ খাই কৈ। (kew more bill cheche, kew khay koy)</p> <p>One’s sacrifice others take benefits</p>	<p>Chinese idioms used meaningfully, the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.</p>
<p>8. 狼吞虎咽 (láng tūn hǔ yàn): “to brush away food like a wolf”</p>	<p>ঝোপ বুঝে কোপ মারা (Jhop bujhe kop mara)</p> <p>As the wind blows, you must set your sail.</p>	<p>Chinese idioms used meaningfully, the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.</p>
<p>9. 见利忘义 (jiàn lì wàng yì): “to forget integrity so as to achieve gain”</p>	<p>Kazer somoy kazi kaz furale paji Get rid of one who has served the purpose.</p>	<p>Chinese idioms used meaningfully, the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.</p>

10. 缘木求鱼 (yuán mù qiú yú): “to use counterproductive methods to do something”	Dhori mach na chui pani To make sure of something without risking anything.	Chinese idioms used meaningfully, almost the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.
11. 开卷有益 (kāi juàn yǒu yì): “reading always brings benefits”	Sikkha i jatir merudondo Education is the backbone of a nation.	Chinese idioms used meaningfully, almost the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.
12. 相濡以沫 (xiāngrúyǐmò): “to help each other out despite both being in delicate condition”	নুন খায় আর গুন গাই তার। (Nun khay ar gun na gay) to help the one who help you	Chinese idioms used meaningfully, almost the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb.
13. 难兄难弟 (nànxīōngnàndì): “brothers of misfortune”	অভাগা যেদিকে চায় সাগর শুকিয়ে যায়। (Ovaga jedike chay sagor sukiye jay) A misfortune person.	Chinese idioms used meaningfully, almost the same in Bengali language as Bengali proverb
14. 傲慢的軍隊肯定會輸掉這場戰鬥 An arrogant army will lose the battle for sure.	অতি দর্পে হোতা লঙ্কা (Otidorpe hota lanka.) Excessive bravado ruined the great kingdom of Lanka. Pride goes before fall.	This Chinese proverb is meaningfully used in Bengali as idioms than proverbs.
15. 火上加油 (huǒ shàng jiā yóu): “to throw fuel on the fire”	আগুনে ঘি ঢালা (Agune ghee dhala) to throw fuel on the fire	This Chinese idiom is meaningfully used in Bengali as proverb
16. 笑里藏刀 (xiàolǐcángdāo): “a dagger hidden behind a smile”	মুখে মধু পেটে বিষ (Mukhe modhu pete bish) a dagger hidden behind a smile	This Chinese idiom is meaningfully used in Bengali as proverb

The differences are mainly probably due to cultural variation in both Chinese and Bengali culture. Where Bengali language is immensely affected by the English language comparatively but Chinese language accepts but some universality is more or less different in case of treating idioms and proverbs, when it comes to any comparison with Bengali language.

But at the same time the similarity also seems common in both languages when it comes to proverb. Most of the Chinese proverbs are commonly found in Bengali proverbs or idioms or in some wise saying of Bengali language. Where the Bengali wise sayings are known as the wise saying but in Chinese more or less they are known as Proverbs as far the comparison indicating in above mentioned table.

Conclusion

Some universal elements are commonly found in Chinese and Bengali Proverbs and idioms. The aim of the research with the cross-cultural analysis found out how proverbs are treated in Chinese and Bengali language. The study found the similarities and also the dissimilarities the way proverbs are treated in both. While analyzing dissimilarities it seems that some Bengali proverbs are based on their meaning found commonly used as Chinese idioms and Chinese proverbs depending on their meaning are found, used as Bengali idioms. This study undoubtedly improve cross-cultural awareness among students; thus foreign language teachers are expected to be inspired by the results of this research as it's completely new field for Bengali language researcher to analyze further depending on the present study's outcomes.

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